

Pest resistance—insects

Influence of rice plant morphology on leaffolder incidence

Z. Islam and A. N. M. R. Karim, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

Rice crops in Bangladesh are attacked by three rice leaffolder species: *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley, and *M. exigua* (Butler) (Pyralidae: Lepidoptera). Larvae fold rice leaves lengthwise and feed on the green tissue, sometimes causing severe damage to the plant. We evaluated whether plant morphological characters influence leaffolder incidence.

Sixteen rice varieties and breeding lines were tested in the 1993 aus (summer) season under irrigated condition at the BRRI experimental farm in Gazipur. The experiment used a randomized complete block design with eight replications. Four-week-old seedlings of each entry were transplanted in 1-m² plot at 20-cm² hill spacing. Standard fertilizer and water management and other cultural operations were used. From booting to dough stages, three hills from each plot were selected at random for data collection. Border hills were not used. Plant height, number of total and folded leaves, and length and width of three flag leaves were determined.

Rice plant morphological characters and incidence of folded leaves caused by leaffolders. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1993 aus.*

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Green leaves hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Leaf blade (cm)		Folded leaves	
			Length	Width	(no. hill ⁻¹)	(%)
TKM6	147	42	56.1	1.04	0.38	0.9
IR32419-81-2-3-3	90	18	34.4	1.33	0.46	2.9
BR42419-44-2-3-2	97	19	32.4	1.28	0.58	3.0
S818B-10-2	91	32	32.2	1.34	0.63	2.2
BR4909-R1-R2	107	20	36.1	1.53	0.71	3.9
BR21	103	11	30.2	1.33	0.75	7.4
IR7156-J20-3-2-1-1	104	26	33.6	1.50	0.92	4.2
IR35366-40-3-3-2-2	93	25	32.6	1.32	0.96	3.9
IR31805-20-1-3-3	96	21	32.7	1.28	1.00	5.7
BR20	112	22	37.2	1.52	1.00	4.8
RP1442-2-2-3-5-1	87	18	30.5	1.31	1.21	6.9
BR1	82	19	33.1	1.25	1.25	7.1
IR42015-83-3-2-2	78	22	31.3	1.29	1.29	6.4
BR4490-B-69	108	28	36.9	1.54	1.46	5.1
B532B-PN-1-MS-1-KP-1	90	31	29.0	1.39	1.54	6.0
Purbachi	98	15	28.6	1.67	1.88	14.1
Mean	99	23	34.2	1.37	1.01	5.3
P < (ANOVA)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
cv%	3.9	-	9.7	10.2	-	-

*Data are av of 8 replications.

Test entries differed in plant height, number of green leaves hill⁻¹, and leaf blade length and width (see table). On average, leaffolders had folded 5.3% (0.9-14.1%) of the leaves. The entries also differed in rate of the incidence of folded leaves. Leaffolder-resistant variety TKM6, with narrow and long leaves, had the lowest level of folded leaves (0.9%), while Purbachi, with wide and short leaves, had the highest level (14.1%). There was no correlation between

folded leaves and plant height ($r = -0.336$) or green leaf number ($r = -0.0195$). However, the incidence of folded leaves was negatively correlated with leaf blade length ($r = -0.507$, $P < 0.05$) and positively correlated with leaf blade width ($r = 0.551$, $P < 0.05$). Results indicated that narrow and long leaves may offer some resistance against leaffolders compared with wide and short leaves in rice plants. ■

A virulent rice gall midge biotype in Manipur

M. P. Singh, Entomology Department, College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University, Imphal, Manipur, India

Five biotypes of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason have been identified in India. The GM population of Manipur was earlier described as biotype 3 of India, which conformed to the Ranchi GM biotype. However, a new pattern of reaction to differential rice varieties has been observed since 1991.

We evaluated a standard set of 10 differentials in four groups against the GM population of Iroisemba, Manipur, India

during the 1991-94 wet seasons. Thirty-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted in 3-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing.

Local recommended agronomic practices were followed. Gall midge incidence was recorded at 50 d after transplanting.

Reaction of differential rice varieties to gall midge (GM). Iroisemba, Manipur, India. 1991-94.

Group	Differential	GM incidence (%)									
		1991		1992		1993		1994		Mean	
		Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers
I	W1263	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ARC6605	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
II	Phalguna	70	14.5	80	19.0	80	28.7	50	22.0	70	21.1
	ARC5984	60	11.9	35	11.7	95	21.0	70	18.0	65	15.7
III	CR-MR1523	65	13.5	50	15.2	60	22.0	35	10.6	52.5	15.3
	Velluthacheera	25	7.5	20	8.2	65	14.2	10	2.9	30	8.2
	Aganni	45	8.2	35	14.8	60	25.9	15	2.9	38.8	13.0
	Ptb10	30	8.1	40	10.2	85	16.1	35	6.5	47.5	10.2
IV	T1477	45	10.8	30	10.9	60	17.0	55	12.7	47.5	12.9
	TN1	80	22.7	65	17.5	95	27.0	60	15.8	75	20.8